
THE IMPORTANCE OF UTILIZING LOCATIVE SEMANTICS

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Annotation: This article devoted to open the theme the importance of utilizing locative semantics. On the other hand, ways of expressing locative adessive elements in English and Uzbek languages were comperatively studied.

Key words: *separative case, locative ablative, adessive elements, semiconductor, plausible bound, approximative mode, the cofinal, the coinitial.*

In grammar, the locative case is a grammatical case which indicates a location. It corresponds vaguely to the English prepositions "in", "on", "at", and "by". The locative case belongs to the general local cases, together with the lative and separative case. The locative case exists in many language groups. It is known that adverbial modifier is secondary part of speech which denotes various peculiarities of action: aim, reason, condition, degree, time and place. The term "locative" means the location of a person or an object. "Adessive" as a new linguistic term means "categorical form of case, indicating the location, belonging, instrument of n action". In modern linguistic some grammarians called it simply "locative" or "private locative". But this term is not in frequent use by linguists. This term is not totally differed from locative ablative, locative translative (linguistic term), locative allative, locative possessive and so on. That's why it would be better use locative adessive as it shows full location human-beings or objects. Syntactical units, expressing locative adessive components can be defined in the position of dependent componential relations with core components on the base of subordinate connection. So in this article we tried to point two main problems:

1. Ways of expressing locative adessive elements;

2. Their variants which can be connotative, selective and adverbial in English and Uzbek languages.

The ways of expressing locative adessive elements in English can be expressed with the help of various types of prepositions and nouns, denoting places and locations[1]. Linguist Sweet H. made out the following classification of adverbial modifier: adverbial modifier of place, adverbial modifier of time, adverbial modifier of reason, adverbial modifier of consequence, adverbial modifier of way of action. Some Russian scientists call the locative adessive semas as —private locative or in ordinary way —locative[2].

In English examples the locative instrumental sema is mainly represented by the combination of nouns representing vehicles, body parts with the different prepositions of space and means in the performance of work:

1. I scrambled to my feet;
2. Every animal was shown on the curtain;
3. He spent most of his time in the saddle.

In the examples given it is possible to replace —to my feet, on the curtain, in the saddle with the adverbial elements if it is intended to determine whether the units are in the semiconductor. In addition to the —by means of, by virtue of, with the help of, with the aid of, by dint of determination of instrumentality these transformations can be used.

Other variants of locative semas are divided into groups of locative allative, locative ablative, locative translative, locative possessive. In our opinion, if we call the elements which reflect the attitude of place with the term locative adessive it will give a chance to have more precise imagination about these forms. In the dictionary of O.S.Axmanova the word —adessive is defined: —...it is the categorical form which indicates locative possessive, way of action meaning of case[3]. The term —locative adessive is used in some monographic works. Locative adessive sema expresses the syntactic forms which reflect person, the location of subject, taking place from that location and also occurring an action in the location.

In English language we can see that locative adessive sema is reflected with noun with the help of different prepositions:

1. At+N: We spent two very pleasant days at Oxford;
2. In+N: I dropped at the train in Milan;
3. On+N: We had decided to sleep on board;
4. Across+N: Susie heard Dr. Porhoit slip his hand across the river
5. Over+N: The oldman has was leaning over the chair ;
6. Under+N: This will keep you safe under the water;
7. By+N: At Abingdon the river possess by the streets;
8. In the middle of +N or in the centre of +N: I was just in the middle of a set;
9. In front of +N: This card will be given you at 3 o'clock tomorrow in front of Westminster Abbey;
10. Opposite +N: We were almost opposite the hotel now .

And also, we can see that this syntaxeme is used in the combinations like: near+N, behind + N, inside+ N, on the other side of+N, between+N, round+N in different texts. Locative adessive sema reflects especially the place of action, subject and person. But, we should note that in Uzbek the suffix of case – да which reflects time and place reflects not only locative adessive syntaxemes but also temporal syntaxeme. For example: У мактабда ўқийди. У ёзда дам олади.

In Uzbek language locative adessive syntaxeme is formed not only with the help of suffix-da, but also with the help of particle.

1. S + da: Endi cherkovda toat-ibodat etasan! ;
2. S + oldida: Bolalar oldida joyboy bermadim ;
3. S + lar + da: Bpigadir majlislarda ishtirok etadi;
4. S + orasida: Har qator orasida bittadan panjara qo'ydim;
5. S + chetida: Tandir chetida cho'nqayib o'tirdim;
6. S + ichida: Bir g'o'zam jo'ya ichida bo'ldi;
7. S + ketida: Shiypon ketida iyak-chakkasini po'moli bilan o'rab turdi;
8. S + ostida: Ayolim qayrag'och ostida beshikka suyanib yig'ladi;

9. S + betida: Yer betida qolgan cho'pni terib olaberdi;

10. S + boshida: Men dala boshida bo'laman.

We shall argue that locative expressions universally consist of two layers, one for the configuration and one for the mode. The configuration describes the way in which several objects are positioned with respect to each other. Configurations can be brought into correspondence with prepositions which do not indicate change of location. Examples are: at, in, on, between, in front of etc. The mode on the other hand describes the way in which an object moves with respect to the named configuration. While there is no plausible bound on the number of configurations that a language distinguishes, the number of modes seems to be limited: there is evidence for the static, the cofinal, the cointial, the transitory and the approximative mode. A mode is static if the object remains in that configuration during event time (e. g. Finnish inessive *talossa*, in the house); the mode is cofinal if the object moves into the configuration during event time (e. g. Finnish illative *taloon*, into the house); the mode is cointial if the object moves from the configuration. We shall argue that locative expressions universally consist of two layers, one for the configuration and one for the mode.

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(e. g. Finnish relative *talosta*, out of the house). The mode is transitory if the object moves in and again out of the configuration (e. g. through the tunnel). Finally, the approximative mode describes a movement approaching a configuration (e. g. towards the tunnel). From a semantical and syntactical point of view a locative expression is therefore structured as follows. [M [L DP]] , where M is a modaliser (specifying the mode), L a localiser (specifying the configuration) and DP a determiner phrase. It may be the case that L precedes DP (as in English) or that it follows it and the same for M. In most languages which we have looked at, L and M end up on the same side of the DP, but they need not (as is the case in Chinese)[4].

In the summary it should be noted that locativeness category in the English and Uzbek languages there were sorted out locative adessive, locative allative, locative ablative, locative translative, locative instrumental syntaxemes their distinctive features were defined and their connecting opportunities with other syntaxemes were depicted on the basis of subordinative connection. It was shown that other approaches to locative semantics fail to recognize important distinctions (e.g., explicit/implicit), fall prey to some misconceptions of the relation of language and space (e.g., RO-centered search regions), and on the whole are descriptive at best. It was argued that neither regions or vectors, nor image schemas or functions, are of primary importance for locative semantics. Rather, the representational aspects of the mental presentation of a scene, the processing aspects of its attentional perspectivation, the selection of conceptual elements for speaking during language generation and the conventionality of semantics must be regarded as central for an explanatory account of the specification and cross-linguistic variation of locative semantics.

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